

INTRODUCTION

Attracting foreign investment is an essential factor in economic growth and regional development. Foreign investments can help create new jobs, increase tax revenues, and develop infrastructure, improving the population's quality of life.

Attracting foreign investment can diversify the economy for many regions that depend on certain industries. This reduces the risks associated with fluctuations in commodity prices or economic crises.

Studying the aspects of attracting foreign investment allows us to identify the problems and barriers investors face. This can help develop recommendations for improving the investment climate, which is an essential task for the authorities.

In Russia's new geopolitical and macroeconomic reality, a transition is underway to a new development model based on internal financial, monetary, labor, institutional, and other resources. This model would accelerate the economy's structural transformation, change priorities in foreign economic relations, and ensure the consolidation of society.

Investments, as is well known, are a determining factor in economic growth and, consequently, the social well-being of the population of any state. In conditions of high uncertainty and financial sanctions, investments and consumer demand are considered key development sources for the Russian state. Balanced and sustainable economic growth will become the basis for achieving national development goals. Intensification of business investment activities at the expense of its financial resources will contribute to ensuring the stability of conditions for investors, risk sharing, and encouraging investments in technological and infrastructure projects.

Tax incentives are one of the most sought-after tools that stimulate investment in the regional economy. Today, in the scientific literature, the question of the economic content of tax benefits, their types, and the scale of their application is debatable, which has a contradictory effect on their practical use as tax expenditures, as shortfall revenues of the budgets of the budgetary system of the Russian Federation. The above confirms the relevance of this problem and can be supplemented by consideration of the practical aspects of tax support for investors in the region. The purpose of the study is to substantiate proposals for improving tax legislation in terms of expanding the tax powers of state authorities of the subjects of the Russian Federation, improving taxation of profits and property of organizations, and improving the investment climate.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. I. Tikhonov et al. believe that the availability of direct investments and venture capital largely determines the number of innovative projects in terms of financial resources and supporting the infrastructure necessary for the project's success. According to the authors, the proposed multi-criteria optimization model makes it possible to determine a set of target values of key performance indicators (KPIs) corresponding to such investments [1].

A. B. Andreu and K. Lavoratori confirm the hypothesis that past colonial relations and historical context influence decisions on foreign direct investment. The authors demonstrate the importance of the historical context in international business research and emphasize that former colonial influence continues to provide advantages to some countries, including attracting foreign direct investment [2].

A. Cuervo-Cazurra et al. write that financial and tax incentives effectively attract investment projects, as they reduce short-term creation costs and long-term operating costs, respectively. The authors find that economic incentives are more effective for attracting projects from scratch in countries with high-quality institutions. In contrast, tax incentives are more effective in countries with low-quality institutions [3].

H. Khan also emphasizes the importance of institutional quality and a sound governance system to attract foreign direct investment. The author shows that only the quality of regulation significantly increases investment inflows. In contrast, other institutional indicators on the institutional quality index are negatively related to inflows in a global sense [4]. B. Bergougui and S. M. Murshed also believe that improving institutional quality is the key to attracting more FDI into the manufacturing and service sectors [5].

J. R. Faria et al. write that the government can attract entrepreneurs to develop their businesses by offering various incentives, particularly encouraging skilled migration to the region. The authors conclude that the government can create a favorable environment for business creation rather than relying solely on government investments [6].

D. Naeher and R. Narayanan show that many low-income countries, especially in Africa and South Asia, are approaching adequate private capital attraction. Given their limited resources, these countries are performing well, according to the authors [7].

G. Pantelopoulos believes human capital is vital in public investment [8]. G. Biglizer et al. They write that internal unrest, especially violent conflicts, increases political risk and deters foreign direct investment. The authors' results show that Chinese companies prefer higher-risk investments [9]. F. Rentz believes that the number of patent applications in the host European countries significantly positively impacts the inflow of Chinese investment.

The author shows that the policy of the European Union can become an effective tool for managing Chinese investments [10].

A. Karakhan & M. Bayır show that expansionary monetary policy before and during COVID-19 stimulates direct investment inflow to developing countries, causing a high global stock market index and low interest rates [11].

A. N. N. Le et al. analyze how trade openness and political stability affect foreign direct investment in 25 countries in the Asia-Pacific region. The authors' results show that trade openness positively affects investment, while political stability has an adverse effect [12].

H. Huang writes that increased number of temporary migrant workers in China per person is due to a decrease in foreign direct investment of \$259. The author suggests that foreign direct investment may decline with the increased number of migrants, which will help avoid losses from urbanization in these cities [13].

R. V. Cayetano et al. conclude that outgoing foreign direct investment is not conditioned by environmental regulation, and the quality of regulation in the European Union improves its balance of foreign investment [14].

A. Njuguna & E. Nnadozie study the relationship between ease of doing business as one of the investment climate indicators, and the inflow of foreign direct investment into Africa. According to the authors, ease of doing business plays a positive role in attracting FDI [15]. According to O. E. Ogbonna, this is correct – the author shows that global uncertainty has a significant deterrent effect on FDI inflows to Africa, and economic governance institutions on the continent enhance this impact rather than mitigate it [16].

Thus, various factors, including economic, political, social, and cultural aspects, can influence the attractiveness of a region or a particular country for foreign investors. The scientific problem lies in systematizing and analyzing these factors, identifying their interrelationships, and influencing investment decisions.

There are numerous methods and approaches to assessing the effectiveness of attracting foreign investment, and it is not always clear which one is the most appropriate for a particular region or sector of the economy.

Political and economic instability can significantly influence foreign investors' decisions. Thus, it is necessary to analyze how various aspects of instability (e.g., corruption, changes in legislation, economic crises) affect investment flows.

Given the changes in the global economy, such as globalization, digitalization, and changing trade flows, regions must adapt to the new conditions. The scientific problem is to explore how regions can effectively respond to these changes and attract investment in the new environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study used general scientific methods of cognition as its methodological basis: systematic, logical, and semantic analysis, synthesis of theoretical and practical materials, and comparison.

The information base was open data posted on the Government of Rostov Oblast portal on the amount of tax benefits provided by regional legislation and on the revenue of Rostov Oblast consolidated budget (CB RO).

The materials for the research were publications in peer-reviewed journals on economics, finance and international relations, which consider the theoretical and empirical aspects of foreign investment, in particular: Management International Review, Journal of International Business Policy, Journal of the Knowledge Economy, Review of World Economics, Small Business Economics, International Economics and Economic Policy, Studies in Comparative International Development.

RESULTS

The use of tax powers granted to the legislative bodies of the subjects of the Russian Federation by the Tax Code of the Russian Federation allows them to manage individual elements of taxes that stimulate the inflow of investments [17]. These taxes include two direct taxes – corporate income tax (federal tax) and corporate property tax (regional tax). The tax powers of the sub-federal government are limited by the provisions of the legislation on taxes and fees, which reduces their tax independence. We believe its expansion will contribute to increased investment and dynamic regional development.

Let us analyze the results of tax support for investors in Rostov Oblast, one of the leading regions of the Russian Federation in attracting investments, developing engineering and transport infrastructure, implementing an effective system of administrative procedures, cooperating between government and business, and providing opportunities for business development.

The Rostov Oblast Investment Portal is an electronic resource with cartographic characteristics and a register of investment projects. The Rostov Oblast Investment Development Agency Partner Association is an operational center for investment project support. Inter-budget transfer availability and tax preferences determine the region's investment attractiveness. The main tools of tax accounting are benefits, property tax, income tax, and deductions, such as investment tax deduction.

Since 2012, Rostov Oblast is governed by the Regional Law “On Regional Taxes and Certain Taxation Issues in Rostov Oblast”, which implements the tax powers of the Legislative Assembly of Rostov Oblast by establishing tax benefits in four areas, including support for investment activities [18]. In 2022, the region introduced a Regional Investment Standard to create an understandable, transparent investment ecosystem.

In 2021-2022, Rostov Oblast was granted investment tax benefits for corporate income tax in the form of:

- a reduced tax rate credited to regional budget revenues of 13.5% for organizations engaged in investment activities (reduced from 17.0% by 3.5 percentage points). Starting in 2025, this rate will be abolished;
- a tax rate of 0% for organizations that have the status of a resident of a priority development area for five tax periods (5 calendar years), as well as for organizations that concluded a special investment contract;
- a reduced tax rate of 10% for participants in regional investment contracts, regardless of the volume of capital investments (reduced from 17.0% by seven percentage points). This rate will be valid until 31.12.2028.

Investor organizations can also take advantage of the investment tax deduction (ITD) for income tax introduced in Rostov Oblast in 2020. The ITD allows the taxpayer to reduce the amount of tax and advance payments at a time due to the costs of acquiring or constructing fixed assets and the costs of their refinement, modernization, and reconstruction. In the region, this tax deduction is established for organizations involved in the processing and preservation of meat, meat products and dairy products, in participating in the national project “Labor Productivity”, and operating in the field of telecommunications (since 2022) [19].

Income tax payers engaged in investment activities received tax support for 1561.3 million RUR in 2021 and 2343.0 million RUR in 2022. As you can see, its volumes increased by 150.1%. The main growth is associated with using ITD, which indicates its demand among the Don business and is a mechanism for encouraging investment activity [20].

Let us pay attention to the following circumstance: like all Russian regions where the corporate income tax levy has been introduced, Rostov Oblast received a grant from the federal budget since 2021 to compensate for the shortfall in budget revenues, partially confirming the implementation of the regional investment standard. It can amount up to 200 million RUR for each investor organization unrelated to gambling, mining, financial, or insurance activities. Consequently, subsidies to the region to compensate for the ITD can stimulate its use and strengthen the sustainability of the regional budget.

We consider it appropriate to grant the subjects of the Russian Federation the right to lower the corporate income tax rate for industries with promising economic specialization,

the development of which will reduce the level of interregional differentiation of the socio-economic state of the regions and accelerate their financial growth. The list of such industries for each subject of the Russian Federation is presented in the “Spatial Development Strategy of the Russian Federation for the period up to 2025”. For example, 27 branches of promising economic specialization were identified for Rostov Oblast, 21 for the Republic of Crimea, and 23 for the Republic of Bashkortostan. Moreover, a subject of the Russian Federation may extend ITD to some of these industries, justifying its choice. We believe that at the present stage, it is necessary to provide the subjects of the Russian Federation with more tax independence in managing the regional component of the corporate income tax rate while maintaining tax conditions.

In Rostov Oblast, during the analyzed period, there were two types of investment-related tax benefits for corporate property tax: a reduced tax rate and exemption for specific categories of investor organizations. The most demanded benefit was provided to the participants of the investment project in the form of a reduced rate of 1.1% concerning newly created and acquired property [21]. The volume of tax support for property tax payers engaged in investment activities in the Don region amounted to 1928.7 million RUR in 2021. and 1972.2 million RUR in 2022, having increased slightly, by 102.3% [22].

As shown by the analysis of open data from the Government of Rostov Oblast (see Table. 1), the total amount of tax benefits provided by regional legislation reached 8409.8 million RUR in 2022 and increased by 132.6% compared to the previous year, and by 129.3% compared to the pandemic year of 2020.

Table 1

Dynamics of tax benefits provided by the legislation of Rostov Oblast in 2020-2022
will be million rubles [Ibid.]

Indicators	2020	2021	2022	2022 by 2021, %	2022 by 2020, %
1. Tax benefits, total including:	6503.9	6341.5	8409.8	132.6	129,3
of an investment nature	2567.2	3490.0	4345.7	124.5	169,3
2. Share of investment tax benefits in the total amount of tax benefits, %	39.5	55.0	51.7		
3. Tax and non-tax revenues of CB RO	185447.3	218077.9	249246.7	114.3	134,4
4. The share of investment tax benefits in the amount of tax and non-tax revenues of CB RO, %	1.4	1.6	1.7		

The volume of tax support for investors amounted to 2,567.2 million RUR in 2020, and its share in the total tax benefits was 39.5%. In 2021, it amounted to 3,490.0 million RUR and 51.7%, respectively. In 2022, these indicators were improved and amounted to 4,345.7 million RUR and 51.8%, respectively. The share of investment tax benefits is insignificant in the tax and non-tax revenues of CB RO, which is confirmed by the following data: 1.4% in 2020, 1.6% in 2021, and 1.7% in 2022. We believe it can be increased by implementing the author's proposals.

An assessment of investment tax benefits conducted by their supervisor, the Ministry of Economic Development of Rostov Oblast, showed a stimulating effect during the five years of validity, a positive impact on the budget, and the need to reform corporate property tax benefits. Therefore, since 2023, there have been two types of updated property tax benefits for organizations in the territory of the Don region:

- in the form of full exemption from taxation: a) property newly created as part of an investment project with investments of 300 million RUR or more, or carried out on the territory of an industrial (industrial) park; b) organizations that have the status of residents of priority development territories or concluded concession agreements on the creation and operation of a tram network;
- in the form of a 50% reduced tax amount: a) for organizations engaged in the telecommunications sector, about communication facilities and data centers; b) for organizations that have invested up to 300.0 million RUR, depending on the territory of sale, about newly created property within the framework of the investment project [23].

As known, two bases exist for calculating corporate property tax: 1) the average annual cost of property and 2) the cadastral value for certain facilities – administrative and business centers, shopping centers and premises in them, certain non-residential premises, including those used for offices, retail facilities, consumer services and catering facilities. The subject of the Russian Federation granted the right from the established list to form the annual composition of real estate objects for which the cadastral value acts as the tax base.

The problems of determining the principles and methods of cadastral valuation have a destructive effect on the quality of taxation and require a change in the methodology of cadastral valuation, which must apply to assessing a significant array of objects while considering their specifics.

Perhaps for this reason, work continues in Rostov Oblast on forming a list of real estate objects for which the tax base is defined as the cadastral value. Other reasons include supporting entrepreneurship and avoiding the projected increase in the tax burden in modern conditions.

The Benefits Effectiveness software package, developed by the Federal Tax Service of the Russian Federation in cooperation with the Ministry of Finance of the Russian Federation, will

allow for a comparative analysis of regional practices in applying tax benefits, evaluating their effectiveness, canceling ineffective ones, and saving budget funds that can be used to support individual industries and citizens.

To ensure a balanced regional budget, stable corporate property tax receipts, and lower administrative (tax) costs, we consider it necessary to finalize the legal framework regarding terminology and methods for determining the cadastral value of property, suspending for this time the formation by the executive authorities of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation of an annual list of administrative, business and commercial facilities for which the cadastral value is set for calculating corporate property tax.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Notably, using a systematic approach to forming a favorable investment climate in Rostov Oblast seems successful. A significant role in this system is given to tax support that stimulates business investment activity. An analysis of regional practice has shown that two direct taxes from organizations are used for this purpose – income tax and property tax. CB RO's shortfall in income from the provision of investment tax benefits accounts for an insignificant share, less than 2%, of revenue. It seems necessary to expand the powers of the sub-federal authorities on these taxes and continue improving the mechanisms of investment and taxation of commercial and office property, which will stimulate investment in the regions to accelerate technological and infrastructural development.

Tax benefits cannot be a decisive factor in increasing investment activity alone. Still, they will allow tax payments to be reduced within certain limits over a specific period to pay off the loan and accrued interest gradually.

Given the changes in the global economy, such as globalization, digitalization, and changing trade flows, regions must adapt to the new conditions. Research on the aspects of attracting foreign investment can help regions develop strategies that promote their sustainable development.

Studying the factors influencing the attraction of foreign investments can lead to the development of more effective strategies and policies at the regional and national levels [24]. This may include improving the investment climate, creating special economic zones, and introducing tax incentives.

Considering global challenges such as climate change and social inequality, the study of foreign investments can focus on their role in sustainable development. This includes analyzing investments' environmental and social impacts and developing recommendations to minimize them.

Studying the impact of political stability and the legal environment on attracting foreign investment may be an important area for future research. This can help develop recommendations to improve the legal framework and increase investor confidence. In particular, research literature offers no definitive results regarding the impact of diplomatic relations on international flows [25].

Given the instability in world markets and the political situation, studying the risks associated with attracting foreign investment is becoming increasingly relevant [26]. This can help regions better prepare for possible economic shocks.

Thus, research in this area can contribute to a deeper understanding of the mechanisms for attracting foreign investment and their impact on regional economic and social development.

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